

Does Government Digitization Reform Reduce Cities Natural Resource Dependence

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Online Publication: 09 September 2025	Against the backdrop of increasing globalisation and digitisation, the resource curse continues to constrain the economic and social development of some resource-rich regions. How to alleviate the resource curse, optimise resource allocation and achieve sustainable development is the core issue of concern for governments and academics. In this context, government digital reform (GDD) is seen as a possible solution path. Government Digital Reform has opened up new paths to alleviate the resource curse dilemma. This study utilizes the data of Chinese prefecture-level cities from 2011 to 2020 to delve into the effects of GDD on the degree of natural resource dependence (RSD). The main findings are as follows: first, GDD significantly mitigates urban RSD. second, the effect of GDD on attenuating RSD geographically exhibits a trend of west > central > east; moreover, this effect is particularly significant in third- and fourth-tier cities as well as those with relatively low levels of digital finance and marketization. Finally, GDD further reduces urban RSD by optimizing the allocation of land resources, promoting the development of the digital economy (DE), and raising public awareness of environmental issues. Overall, the research in this paper provides us with a new perspective to deeply explore the formation mechanism and change trend of RSD from the perspective of GDD. This provides important theoretical support and practical guidance for relevant policy makers, and helps to promote resource-based cities to achieve green, low-carbon and sustainable development in the era of digital economy.
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1. INTRODUCTION

With the development of globalization and continuous environmental degradation, the problem of urban RSD has become increasingly prominent (Hossain et al.,2023). Over-dependence on natural resources, especially non-renewable resources, tends to lead to the resource curse,

which affects long-term economic growth, social welfare and ecological balance (Shao & Yang, 2014). This dependence not only limits the innovative capacity and diversity of the economy, but can also lead to resource depletion, ecological deterioration, and long-term economic volatility (Zhang et al., 2023). Therefore, exploring ways to reduce urban dependence

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on natural resources, especially in the context of economic transformation and sustainable development, has become a central concern for economists and policy makers.

Figure 1 shows the kernel density estimates of resource dependence for Chinese cities in 2011 and 2020. By comparing the two curves, we can draw a conclusion about the change in resource dependence of Chinese cities during

this decade, i.e., the curve in 2020 is more to the right or higher than the curve in 2011, which means that more cities have increased their resource dependence during this decade. This conclusion indicates that China's RSD is increasing rather than decreasing and that a solution to its urban natural resource dependence problem is imminent.

Figure 1 Kernel density map of urban resource dependence

GDD, as a global trend in recent years, provides new perspectives and tools to address the above issues (Asgarkhani, 2005). Digital reforms not only improve the efficiency of government decision-making, but also provide more precise and transparent means for resource allocation, market access and environmental regulation (Höchtel et al., 2016; Deichmann et al., 2016). Through digital means, governments can more effectively monitor resource use, promote rational resource allocation, and facilitate environmental protection and sustainable development (Castro et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2023). Especially in the current information age, the interaction between GDD and resource management provides an ideal platform for exploring how to realize the harmonious development of economy, society and environment through technological and policy innovations.

In a related study on RSD, Auty (2002) first suggested that when regions or countries are endowed with abundant natural resources, these endowments are not always favorable to their economic development, but instead may become a straitjacket to economic growth. Evidence for this hypothesis suggests that an abundance of natural resources may inhibit the development of human capital and technological innovation and weaken the role of institutional norms (She &

Mabrouk, 2023). Among other things, a boom in natural resource industries may increase the opportunity cost of human capital and innovation because these industries pay high wages but do not require high quality labor (Mousavi & Clark, 2021; Cheng et al., 2020). As a result, people may neglect education and innovation (Zhao et al., 2023). In addition, resource exploitation may lead to environmental pollution, which may cause highly qualified labor to leave the area (Klasic et al., 2022). Institutional weakness means that resource-rich areas may be subject to corruption and rent-seeking, leading to a decline in the normative role of institutions (Kolstad & Søreide, 2009). This may increase social conflict and instability, thus negatively affecting economic and social development (Destek et al., 2023). However, these studies have also been questioned. Some critics argue that empirical studies do not clearly distinguish between natural resource abundance and natural resource dependence (Badeeb et al., 2017; Adhikari et al., 2023). The two are quite different concepts: the former reflects the total amount or abundance of resources, while the latter reflects the degree of resource dependence of a country or region's economy. It has been found that over-dependence on natural resources and resource industries may lead to slow economic

growth, while the abundance of natural resources itself does not necessarily have a negative impact. Therefore, when discussing the "resource curse", we should focus on resource dependence, not just resource abundance.

Against this backdrop, the advancement of GDD offers new solutions to this long-standing problem. By implementing digitalization strategies, governments can improve the efficiency of public services, increase transparency, and regulate the use of resources more effectively (Gan et al., 2023; Hidayat et al., 2023). Especially in China, with the rapid economic development, the large-scale exploitation of natural resources has also brought about an obvious resource curse effect (Ahmad et al., 2021; Rongwei & Xiaoying, 2020; Xie et al., 2021). However, with the deepening of digital reforms, these resource-rich regions are expected to break away from the traditional economic growth model and shift to a more sustainable and efficient development path (Chang et al., 2023; Arslan et al., 2022). However, there is a gap in existing articles on GDD and natural resource dependence. Based on this, this paper empirically examines the relationship between GDD and urban RSD using a sample of Chinese prefecture-level cities from 2011-2020.

This study makes important contributions to the literature in related fields in the following ways: first, a novel research perspective. While past studies have focused on the relationship between natural resource abundance and economic growth, this paper provides the first in-depth exploration of how GDD affects natural resource dependence. This provides a new and more nuanced perspective for understanding the resource curse problem. Second, the geographical heterogeneity is explored in depth. By analyzing in detail the different effects of GDD in eastern, central and western regions and city sizes, this study provides an in-depth understanding of the role of geographic factors in the resource curse problem, which provides strong theoretical support for local governments to formulate differentiated policy strategies. Third, the detailed analysis of the degree of marketization. This paper further reveals the significance of this effect in cities with a low degree of digital finance and marketization, providing valuable empirical evidence for urban planning and policy formulation. Fourth, it deepens the understanding of the transmission mechanism. By exploring the three mediating channels of land resource allocation, DE development, and public environmental concern (EC), this study provides a richer and more concrete explanation for understanding how GDD affects RSD, further deepening our understanding of the

complex mechanisms behind the resource curse problem. In summary, this study not only provides new theoretical and empirical evidence for understanding how GDD affects RSD, but also provides useful insights for governments and policy makers on how to more effectively utilize digital tools to promote sustainable development.

The article is structured as follows: the second part delves into the relevant theoretical background. In this part, we systematically elaborate the possible links between GDD and urban RSD and lay a solid theoretical foundation for the subsequent analysis. Part III details the research methodology. This section covers the sources of data, definition of variables, research framework and empirical methods employed, aiming to guarantee the scientific validity and precision of the study. Part IV concentrates on the core empirical analysis and its conclusions. Here, we not only present the main findings of the study, but also ensure the stability and generality of its results through multiple validations. Part V provides a general review of the study and discusses its academic significance and practical implications, as well as providing specific recommendations for policymakers based on the findings.

2. MECHANISMS AND ASSUMPTIONS

2.1 GDD and RSD

The impact of GDD on RSD can be explained in terms of economic mechanisms. First, from the perspective of industrial organization, GDD may lead to changes in market structure. Traditionally, industries that are highly dependent on natural resources, such as mining and agriculture, tend to exhibit highly concentrated market structures in which information asymmetry and market power keep resource allocation away from Pareto efficiency (Lianos & Carballa-Smichowski, 2022). As GDD advances, market information becomes more transparent, allowing small firms and startups to enter and challenge traditional market leaders. This market competition may motivate firms to pursue innovations that reduce their reliance on traditional natural resources. For example, emerging digital technologies such as blockchain can promote supply chain transparency, making renewable resources and sustainable production methods more attractive. Second, from a macroeconomic policy perspective, GDD may have implications for investment and consumption behavior. Traditional economic growth has often been accompanied by a high level of exploitation of natural resources, in large part because natural resources provide countries with immediate fiscal revenues and foreign

exchange reserves without the need for excessive initial investment (Venables, 2016). However, as governments digitize, the collection of taxes and tariffs becomes more efficient, making it more likely that governments will impose taxes on the overexploitation of resources, thereby encouraging more sustainable resource use. In addition, digitization is likely to facilitate the deepening of financial markets, providing firms with more diversified access to finance, thus reducing dependence on natural resource exports. Finally, from a consumer behavior perspective, GDD may change consumer preferences and expectations. As information becomes more transparent, consumers have a clearer understanding of where products come from and how they are made. This may lead consumers to favor products that use sustainable resources and production methods. In addition, digitization may facilitate education and knowledge dissemination, making consumers more aware of the long-term consequences of overexploiting natural resources. In summary, GDD may reduce dependence on natural resources at a profound level by influencing market structures, macroeconomic policies and consumer behavior. This provides a new path to achieve a balance between economic growth and environmental sustainability. Therefore, this paper proposes the following hypothesis:

H1: GDD can significantly reduce urban RSD.

2.2 Effect of GDD on RSD heterogeneity

2.2.1 Impact of heterogeneity in urban location and size

The heterogeneity presented by GDD to RSD, especially in terms of regional differences, relates to regional economic structure, development stage and resource allocation. First, we must recognize that China's three major regions - East, Central and West - have significant differences in economic development, industrial structure and resource endowment. The eastern region has developed a relatively mature market economy system and a high degree of industrial agglomeration due to its early opening up and reform strategies. This has led firms and governments in the eastern region to focus more on improving productivity and innovation in their digital reforms rather than relying excessively on natural resources. In contrast, the central and western regions, especially the west, have long relied more on resource-based industries due to their rich natural resource endowment (Zhu, 2023). This reliance has, to some extent, led to these regions lagging behind in digital reforms. However, as GDD gradually deepens, its potential benefits, such as

improving administrative efficiency, facilitating information sharing and reducing information asymmetry, will have a greater impact on these regions. In resource-rich regions, digital reforms may be seen more as a tool to reduce dependence on natural resources and promote structural transformation of the economy. In addition, GDD may change the competitive strategies among local governments. In the eastern region, as the market is already relatively mature, local governments may focus more on improving the efficiency and quality of public services so as to attract more high-end industries and talents (Brautigam et al., 2018). In the central and western regions, on the other hand, local governments may see digital reforms more as a strategy to attract external investment, improve the efficiency of natural resource use, and promote sustained local economic growth. To summarize, the heterogeneity of GDD to RSD reflects the differences in economic development, industrial structure, and resource endowment across China's regions. Such differences make the effects and impacts of GDD in each region significantly different, which also provides important insights for future policy making.

The effect of GDD on RSD may be heterogeneous across cities of different sizes, and by digging deeper into the nature of economic structure, market development and information mobility, we conduct a series of theoretical derivations. First, city size represents not only the agglomeration of population and economic activities, but also the city's stage of development, market depth and information mobility (Duranton, 1999). In second-tier cities, due to their relatively mature market structure and high degree of information flow, GDD may focus more on improving the quality and efficiency of public services, which is relatively disconnected from natural resource dependence. Tier 5 cities, on the other hand, as marginal areas of economic activity, their infrastructure and market size limit the deep penetration of digital reforms, leading to a weaker link between GDD and natural resource dependence. However, Tier 3 and 4 cities are in a critical period of economic transition. They neither have well-developed market mechanisms like Tier 2 cities, nor are they constrained by infrastructure constraints like Tier 5 cities. These cities are in a critical period of transition from a resource-dependent economy to a more diversified and market-oriented economy. Therefore, GDD may be seen more as a tool for economic transformation in these cities. The introduction and promotion of digital technologies can help these cities improve administrative efficiency, strengthen

resource management and promote optimization of economic structure, thereby reducing their over-reliance on natural resources. In addition, third- and fourth-tier cities are often economically and geographically located at the intersection of resource-rich and economically developed regions, making them more vulnerable to external economic shocks. GDD can help these cities better cope with external shocks, and enable them to develop more robustly in the process of economic transformation by improving information transparency and decision-making efficiency. In summary, this paper proposes the following hypotheses:

H2: The inhibitory effect of GDD on urban natural resource dependence shows heterogeneity in terms of urban location and size.

2.2.2 The impact of heterogeneity in digital finance

The effect of GDD on RSD may differ significantly between cities with different levels of digital finance development, reflecting the profound interaction between information, finance and resource allocation in modern economies (Wan et al., 2023). First, it needs to be clarified why digital finance can play a role in mitigating natural resource dependence. Digital finance, through its efficient information transmission, low-cost transactions and wide coverage, can better provide financial services to enterprises and residents, thus promoting technological innovation, new industry development and economic restructuring. In cities with a high degree of digital finance, economies are more likely to transform from traditional, resource-intensive industries to technology-driven, low-resource-consuming industries. Comparatively, cities with a low degree of digital finance are often accompanied by problems such as imperfections in the financial system, information asymmetry, and high market barriers. Against this backdrop, the impact of GDD is particularly significant. By improving the transparency of public services, optimizing administrative processes and enhancing the efficiency of decision-making, it can to a certain extent make up for the shortcomings of the financial market and promote the transfer of resources from traditional industries to emerging industries (Kuziemski & Misuraca, 2020). This resource redistribution effect is more prominent in cities with a lower degree of digital finance development, as they tend to rely more on government intervention and support to achieve economic transformation and upgrading at the initial stage. In addition, GDD may also contribute to the development and deepening of financial markets through its improvements in information flow, market

trust, and innovation environments (Hao et al., 2023). Especially in cities where digital finance is underdeveloped, government digitization efforts may be more likely to trigger changes and innovations in financial markets, thus accelerating the economic shift from resource-dependent to service- and innovation-oriented. In summary, the more significant mitigating effect of GDD on natural resource dependence in cities with low digital finance development is because these cities are more dependent on government efforts to facilitate economic transformation, and digital reforms are providing the necessary tools and environment for this. Based on the above inferences, this paper proposes the following hypotheses:

H3: The dampening effect of GDD on urban natural resource dependence is more pronounced in regions with lower levels of digital finance.

2.2.3 Impact of heterogeneity in the degree of marketization

This paper will provide theoretical derivations of the heterogeneous effects of the degree of marketization from the following economic dimensions: first, information asymmetry and market failure. Information asymmetry and market frictions tend to be more severe in regions with lower degrees of marketization. In such environments, government digital reforms can play a greater role by improving information transparency, reducing transaction costs and increasing trust among market participants. Through digital platforms and online public services, governments can regulate markets more effectively and reduce market failures, thereby promoting more rational resource allocation. Second, resource allocation and economic restructuring. In regions with a low degree of marketization, resource allocation often relies too much on administrative intervention and the logic of the planned economy (Nutti, 2023). GDD, especially applications such as data analytics and smart government, can help the government carry out macroeconomic regulation and control more scientifically and accurately, and promote the transformation from resource-intensive industries to knowledge- and technology-intensive industries. Third, externalities and public goods supply. In regions where the marketization process is not perfect, the problem of externalities may be more prominent, such as environmental pollution and over-exploitation of public resources, etc. GDD, by improving the efficiency and responsiveness of public service supply, can better manage and solve these externalities, thus reducing the over-dependence on natural resources. Fourth, innovation-driven and economic transformation.

Regions with insufficient marketization may have shortcomings in technological innovation and industrial upgrading (Wigger, 2023). GDD provides these regions with an innovative platform and tools to promote technological research and development (R&D), entrepreneurial activities, and the incubation of new industries, which in turn promotes the optimization and transformation of economic structure. In summary, the mitigating effect of GDD on RSD may be more significant in less market-oriented cities because in these regions, digital reform is not only a manifestation of technological progress, but also an effective means of institutional innovation and economic governance, which provides key support for the deepening of the marketization process and the optimization of economic structure. Based on the above analysis, this paper proposes the following hypotheses:

H4: The dampening effect of GDD on urban natural resource dependence is more pronounced in regions that are much less market-oriented.

2.3 Mediating effect of land resource mismatch (LRM) on RSD of GDD impacts

When we take a deeper look at how GDD can reduce LRM, a core idea emerges. GDD, in essence, is a process that utilizes modern information technology, such as big data, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence, to improve the transparency, accuracy, and efficiency of government decision-making. In the context of land resource management, this means being able to present real-time, openly available information on land use, property ownership, and vacancy for all stakeholders, thereby reducing transaction friction caused by information asymmetry (Fleming et al., 2022). More importantly, digital means enable the government to predict future changes in land demand through big data and make more rational land planning and utilization decisions. Such precise decision-making and efficient regulatory capabilities will help reduce the mismatch of land resources, thereby ensuring that resources are optimally utilized.

And there is a deep economic link between the misallocation of land resources and the degree of dependence of a country or region on natural resources. First, LRM tends to lead to lower productivity. When land is not utilized efficiently or is used for low-productivity activities, it becomes less productive, making it necessary to rely on more other natural resources in order to meet the demands of economic growth. Secondly, irrational allocation of land

resources may lead to overexploitation of resources in some areas while resources in other areas are wasted (Gebresenbet et al., 2023). This unbalanced pattern of resource utilization can further exacerbate dependence on natural resources. More importantly, the irrational use of land resources may lead to environmental damage and ecological imbalance, forcing economies to rely on more natural resources to maintain ecological balance. Therefore, we can assert that by optimizing the allocation of land resources, GDD helps to reduce the dependence on natural resources to a large extent and lays a solid foundation for achieving sustainable economic development. In summary, this paper puts forward the following hypotheses:

H5: GDD reduces urban RSD by mitigating the degree of LRM and thus

2.4 Mediating effect of DE on RSD of GDD influence

In the theoretical framework of modern economics, the digital transformation of government is seen as a key force driving DE. GDD is not just the introduction and application of information technology, but a fundamental reshaping of government operations and services at a deeper level. This process ensures transparent government decision-making, open access to data, and efficient public services. More specifically, governments set the stage for the rise of DE by providing digital infrastructure such as broadband networks, data centers and cloud services. In addition, by creating friendly policies and regulations, the government has provided an enabling environment for digital innovation, which has stimulated the development of various areas of DE such as e-commerce, digital payments, online education and telemedicine. Thus, there is a clear causal relationship between GDD and the prosperity of DE.

In exploring how DE reduces dependence on natural resources, we must first recognize that DE changes the traditional patterns of production and consumption. In DE, the marginal cost of material production decreases, while the value of services and information increases. For example, streaming services reduce the need for physical media, e-books reduce reliance on paper, and online education and telecommuting reduce the need for transportation and buildings (Aké et al., 2023). These changes imply a greater concentration of economic activity in the digital realm and less direct demand for natural resources. In addition, digital technologies can increase efficiency in the use of resources, for example by optimizing logistics and production through

intelligent supply chain management and predictive maintenance. Thus, DE not only changes the pattern of our demand for resources, but also provides us with new tools and methods to use resources more efficiently and sustainably. This shift plays a key role in reducing the dependence on natural resources. In summary, the following hypotheses are proposed in this paper:

H6: GDD reduces urban RSD by increasing the level of digital financial development and thus.

2.5 Mediating effect of EC on GDD affecting RSD

The interaction between government action and public awareness has received increasing attention in recent years in economics research. First, GDD involves not only improving administrative efficiency and promoting economic growth, but also enhancing the transparency and efficiency of information dissemination. Governments actively communicate the importance of environmental protection, the relevance of public health, and the concept of sustainable development through digital platforms, such as online public services and social media (Ingram et al., 2022). In addition, digital technologies have made environmental data and reports more accessible, allowing the public to learn in real time about air quality, water resource conditions and other key environmental indicators (Adade & de Vries, 2023). This openness and transparency stimulates the public's environmental awareness and promotes more proactive participation in environmental protection initiatives.

Thinking further, when the public becomes more concerned about environmental issues, their consumption and lifestyle choices are also affected. Consumers who are more environmentally conscious may choose more sustainable products and services, such as choosing public transportation over private cars, purchasing organic food over conventional produce, or supporting renewable energy over fossil fuels (Guo et al., 2022). This shift in consumer behavior puts pressure on businesses to shift to more environmentally friendly and sustainable production methods. As a result, this transfer of pressure from consumers to producers leads to less reliance on natural resources. In addition, public environmental concerns may also push policymakers to enact stricter environmental regulations that further reduce dependence on natural resources. Overall, EC, as an important outcome of GDD, mediates the formation of a low resource-dependent economic model. To summarize, this paper proposes the following hypotheses:

H7: The GDD reduces urban RSD by increasing EC and thus.

3. MODEL CONSTRUCTION AND DATA DESCRIPTION

3.1. Modeling

To correct for potential city characteristics and time trend bias in the estimation, we employ a regression framework with double fixed effects. By including city fixed effects, the model effectively controls for city characteristics that are constant or change slowly and are not easily observable, thus reducing omitted variable bias. The model can be expressed as:

$$RSD_{it} = \theta + \partial_1 GDD_{it} + \beta_i X_{it} + v_t + u_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

where RSD_{it} is the RSD of city i at time t . The RSD of city i at time t GDD_{it} quantifies the corresponding GDD level; X_{it} is a vector of control variables. v_t and u_i are time and city fixed effects, respectively; ε_{it} is the error term. The key coefficient ∂_1 measures the marginal effect of GDD on RSD.

In order to explore the mechanism of GDD's effect on the degree of resource dependence, we set up a mediation analysis model. First, model (2) estimates the direct effect of GDR on the mediating variables X (including LRM, DE and EC). Subsequently, model (3) further explored how the mediating variable X affects the target variable RSD. The specific model is as follows:

$$X_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 GDR_{i,t} + \beta_i X_{it} + v_t + u_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

$$RSD_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X_{i,t} + \beta_i X_{it} + v_t + u_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (3)$$

where α_1 reveals the economic importance of the mediating effect, and the other variables are defined as above.

3.2. Description of variables and data sources

3.2.1. explanatory variables

Natural Resource Dependence Degree (RSD): Given that the exploitation of mineral resources is a key factor leading to industrial lag, economic distress and ecological damage, China usually uses the output value or the size of personnel in the regional mining industry to assess the resource-based economy. However, due to the lack of data on the industry's output value in prefecture-level cities, this paper chooses the ratio of mining industry employees to total employees as an indicator of resource dependence.

3.2.2. Explanatory variables

Government Digital Reform (GDD): Through textual analysis of government work reports, this study aims to

measure the government's focus on DE. These reports are key sources of policy. Based on the reports from 2001-2020, we count the word frequencies of digital keywords and compare them with the total word frequencies as a measure of government attention. Referring to the methodology of Liu et al. (2023), we identify 121 keywords, which are categorized into "digital technology" (e.g., big data, blockchain) and "digital application" (e.g., service industry, digital government). We use the word frequency share of these two categories as DT and DA indicators, and combine them into the composite indicator GDD.

3.2.3 Intermediate variables

Land Resource Mismatch (LRM): based on the methodology of Li et al. (2016), we adopt the ratio of the area of land granted by agreement to the area of land actually granted as an indicator of LRM. At the intersection of economic growth and environmental sustainability, efficient allocation of land resources is key. This study further explores how LRM serves as a mediating mechanism that influences GDD and urban dependence on natural resources. Especially in the digital era, how the government's digital strategy interacts with LRM and further influences the resource dependency patterns of cities is a topic to be explored in depth.

Digital Economy (DE): In the digital era, DE has become a key driver of economic growth and urban development. To portray this trend, this study focuses on analyzing the development of the Internet and the application of digital finance in conjunction with city-level data. Based on the methodology of Huang et al. (2019), we selected four core indicators on the Internet: the Internet coverage rate, the proportion of employees in the IT industry, the volume of communication services, and the penetration rate of cell phones, which are derived from the China Urban Statistical Yearbook. In addition, we introduced the digital financial inclusion indicator published by Peking University and Ant Financial Services to measure the degree of digital financial penetration. After principal component analysis, these five indicators are integrated into a composite DE indicator called DE, which provides us with a quantitative view of DE progress.

Public Environmental Concern (EC): Drawing on the methodology of Wang Yuzhe and Zhao Jing (2018), this study selected Baidu's "haze" search volume (including mobile and PC) as a proxy indicator of the public's attention to haze, so as to accurately capture the dynamic changes in public attention.

3.2.4. Control variables

In order to accurately estimate the effect of GDD on RSD, we include a set of economic and social control variables to eliminate potential confounding effects. First, we control for the logarithm of Gross Regional Product (lnGdp) and the logarithm of Gross Regional Product per capita (lnPcgdp), taking into account that the size of the economy and the level of economic development may be related to resource dependence. Second, the degree of financial deepening of the economy, i.e., the ratio of loan balance to GDP (Finance), reflects the extent to which the financial sector supports economic activities, including resource development. In addition, the role of education and scientific research in economic development and technological progress is self-evident, so we consider the share of education and scientific research in the financial budget, specifically the ratio of education expenditure to financial expenditure (EduE) and the ratio of scientific research expenditure to financial expenditure (SciE). Also, the logarithm of the size of the general undergraduate school population (lnEdu) is included, as it reflects the level of human capital accumulation in the region, which may have an impact on the way resources are developed and utilized.

3.3 Data sources and descriptive statistics of variables

In exploring the economic nature of RSD (RSD) and GDD (GDD) in city characteristics, the descriptive statistics in Table 1 reveal an important economic phenomenon: significant heterogeneity among cities in terms of resource dependence and digital reforms. In particular, the mean value of RSD is 0.276, but it ranges from nearly 0 to 2.253, and the data distribution of RSD hints at an interesting economic issue, namely that some cities may be at risk of overdependence on specific natural resources, while others may have successfully diversified their economies. Meanwhile, the mean value of GDD is 2.035, ranging from 0.202 to 4.095, and the statistical properties of GDD point to heterogeneous efforts by different governments to promote digitization. In addition, we note that other key indicators, such as digital adoption (DA) and digital technology (DT), as well as a range of economic and social control variables, such as the logarithm of Gross Regional Product (lnGdp) and the logarithm of Gross Regional Product per capita (lnPcgdp), also exhibit significant variation across cities. These data provide a rich context and a solid foundation for our subsequent in-depth exploration of how GDD affects RSD

Table1 Descriptive Statistics

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max.
RSD	1476	0.276	0.534	0.000100	2.253
GDD	1476	2.035	1.089	0.202	4.095
DA	1476	1.321	0.747	0	2.768
DT	1476	0.699	0.590	0	2.020
lngdp	1476	16.76	0.750	15.44	18.16
lnpgdp	1476	10.73	0.515	9.890	11.70
Finance	1476	0.945	0.462	0.394	2.064
EduE	1476	0.180	0.0329	0.120	0.241
SciE	1476	0.0170	0.0129	0.00300	0.0480
lnEdu	1476	10.81	1.092	8.740	13.05

4. EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

4.1. Baseline regression results and discussion

In exploring the impact of GDD (GDD) and its sub-indicators on RSD (RSD), the model results in Table 2 provide a number of interesting insights: in column (1), the coefficient of GDD (GDD) on RSD is -0.0252 and significant, with a t-statistic of -4.1606, which implies that natural resource dependence decreases significantly as GDD strengthens. In columns (2) and (3), we further decompose

GDD into digitization application (DA) and digitization technology (DT). Their negative effects on RSD are both significant and numerically similar, indicating that both contribute to reducing resource dependence. As for the control variables, the balance of all loans of financial institutions as a share of GDP (Finance) shows positive coefficients in all models and reaches significant levels in columns (1) and (2). This may imply that financial deepening is associated with higher resource dependence.

Table 2. Benchmark regression results

VARIABLES	(1) RSD	(2) RSD	(3) RSD
GDD	-0.0252*** (-4.1606)		
DA		-0.0253*** (-3.3491)	
DT			-0.0265*** (-3.1767)
lngdp	-0.0850 (-0.9322)	-0.0812 (-0.8786)	-0.0925 (-1.0110)
lnpgdp	0.0224 (0.2947)	0.0130 (0.1677)	0.0093 (0.1208)
Finance	0.0595* (1.7545)	0.0592* (1.7456)	0.0528 (1.5726)
EduE	-0.0888 (-0.2821)	-0.1270 (-0.4017)	-0.0764 (-0.2417)
SciE	0.3688 (0.6653)	0.3033 (0.5405)	0.6504 (1.1529)
lnEdu	-0.0146 (-0.3204)	-0.0124 (-0.2708)	-0.0137 (-0.2995)
Constant	1.6197* (1.7411)	1.6244* (1.7380)	1.8440** (1.9965)

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Year	Y	Y	Y
City	Y	Y	Y
Observations	1,466	1,466	1,466
R-squared	0.9382	0.9379	0.9378

4.2. robustness and endogeneity tests

4.2.1 Robustness Tests

In order to ensure the robustness of the estimation results, we treated the data with before and after tailoring by 5% and re-estimated the model. The key findings are as follows: the negative effect of GDD (GDD) on RSD (RSD) remains significant in model (1) with a coefficient of -0.0241 and a t-statistic of -4.3830 on the reduced-tailed processed data. models (2) and (3) further examine the sub-indicators of GDD, i.e., digital adoption (DA) and digital technology (DT). The negative relationship between the two on RSD also remains

significant on the downscaled data. In summary, our main findings are solidly supported after a before-and-after shrinkage-tailed 5% robustness test. Specifically, both the government's digital reform strategy and its sub-strategies, such as digital applications and technologies, show a significant negative relationship with RSD. This further solidifies our conclusion that government digitization strategies may help cities reduce their dependence on natural resources. This provides important economic insights for policymakers that by strengthening digitization strategies, it may help promote more sustainable patterns of resource use.

Table 3. Robustness test results

VARIABLES	(1) RSD	(2) RSD	(3) RSD
GDD	-0.0241*** (-4.3830)		
DA		-0.0250*** (-3.7706)	
DT			-0.0247*** (-3.1775)
Controls	Y	Y	Y
Year	Y	Y	Y
City	Y	Y	Y
Constant	1.5157** (1.9645)	1.5160* (1.9610)	1.7282** (2.2499)
Observations	1,466	1,466	1,466
R-squared	0.9408	0.9404	0.9402

4.2.2 Endogeneity test

In order to address the potential endogeneity of GDD (GDD), we adopted the distance between the city and Hangzhou (QM) as its instrumental variable. Our rationale for choosing this instrumental variable is based on the diffusion and penetration mechanisms of digital technologies. In particular, digital financial innovations like Alipay usually affect the region near their origin (e.g., Hangzhou) first. Therefore, the distance between the city and Hangzhou can be used as a source of exogenous variation in digital reforms, independent of other factors that may affect the RSD (RSD).

Regarding the first-stage estimation results, using QM as an instrumental variable, we find that it has a significant negative effect on GDD, with a coefficient of -0.0001 and a t-statistic of -2.6171. this suggests that cities farther away from Hangzhou tend to have lower levels of digitization reform. Using the first-stage estimates, we find that GDD has a significant negative effect on RSD, with a coefficient of -1.2336 and a t-statistic of -2.7537. This further confirms our main finding that the GDD strategy exhibits a significant negative relationship with RSD.

Table 4. Endogeneity test results

VARIABLES	(1) GDD	(2) RSD
QM	-0.0001*** (-2.6171)	
GDD		-1.2336*** (-2.7537)
Controls	Y	Y
Year	Y	Y
City	Y	Y
Constant	-2.1101*** (-2.8270)	
Observations	1,476	1,476
R-squared	0.5048	-1.9643

4.3 Heterogeneity analysis

4.2.1. urban location and scale heterogeneity

This study further explores the heterogeneity of the effect of GDD (GDD) on RSD (RSD). From the perspective of geographic regions, eastern cities show a significant negative relationship between digitization reforms and resource dependence, while this effect is stronger in central and western cities. Especially in the West, we observe a significant decrease in resource dependence as digital reforms advance, suggesting that the region may be placing more emphasis on the efficient use of resources in economic development.

From a city-size perspective, second-tier cities do not seem to show a significant impact of digital reforms on resource dependence, which may suggest that in large metropolitan areas digital penetration has reached saturation or that its impact on resource dependence has been neutralized

by other urban characteristics. However, small and medium-sized cities (especially Tier 3 and Tier 4 cities) exhibit a significant decline in resource dependence as a result of digital reforms, suggesting that in these cities digital reforms provide an effective tool to restructure their economies and reduce overdependence on natural resources. Surprisingly, Tier 5 cities do not show a significant relationship between digitization reforms and resource dependence, which may imply that the potential benefits of digitization reforms have not yet been fully realized in these smaller cities.

Overall, these findings highlight the differential role of digital reforms in different urban contexts, providing policymakers with a more nuanced perspective that can help them better target digital reforms for more sustainable economic development.

Table 5. Results of the urban heterogeneity test

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
	city location			city scale			
	the east	central section	western part	second line	third line	four-line	five-line
VARIABLES	RSD	RSD	RSD	RSD	RSD	RSD	RSD
GDD	-0.0075*** (-2.8359)	-0.0272** (-2.5297)	-0.0518*** (-2.9400)	-0.0003 (-0.2318)	-0.0147** (-2.5300)	-0.0223*** (-2.8467)	0.0367 (0.5768)
Controls	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Year	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
City	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Constant	-1.1311* (-1.8868)	1.0800 (0.5822)	-0.7321 (-0.4043)	0.2762 (1.3227)	1.1902 (1.3864)	1.7368 (1.2231)	13.5057** (2.5714)

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Observations	484	498	348	135	506	738	78
R-squared	0.9635	0.9365	0.9288	0.8744	0.9684	0.9409	0.9224

4.2.1. digital finance heterogeneity

This study further analyzes the digital finance heterogeneity effect of the degree of digital financial development (DFD) on GDD (GDD) affecting RSD (RSD). The results show that there is a significant negative correlation between digital reforms and resource dependence in cities with a lower degree of digital finance development. This finding implies that resource dependence significantly decreases with digital reforms in these cities. This reflects the structural transformation of the economy brought about by the digital reforms for these cities, moving from traditional, highly resource-dependent industries to more modern and efficient ones.

However, this relationship is not evident in cities with higher levels of digital finance development. In these cities, the link between digital reforms and resource dependence is

no longer significant. This may imply that as digital finance has become more developed, its interaction with digital reforms may have reached an equilibrium, allowing the impact of digital reforms on resource dependence to be neutralized. Another possible explanation is that in cities with a high degree of digital finance, the economy has already undergone a high degree of restructuring, so that the impact of further digital reforms on resource dependence becomes limited.

Overall, these findings reveal the key role of the degree of development of digital finance in determining how digital reforms affect resource dependence. Provides policymakers with deeper insights on how to promote digital reforms in different financial contexts in order to achieve more balanced and sustainable economic growth.

Table 6. Results of the digital finance heterogeneity test

VARIABLES	(1)	(2)
	Degree of development of digital finance	
	Low	High
	RSD	RSD
GDD	-0.0254*** (-2.7125)	-0.0009 (-0.2957)
Controls	Y	Y
Year	Y	Y
City	Y	Y
Constant	1.1058 (0.5684)	1.3746** (2.5789)
Observations	965	445
R-squared	0.9403	0.9955

4.2.2. market-based heterogeneity

This study also explores the heterogeneous effect of the degree of marketization on the impact of GDD (GDD) on RSD (RSD). Among cities with a lower degree of marketization, we find a significant negative correlation between digital reforms and resource dependence. Specifically, resource dependence significantly decreases in these cities as digital reforms deepen. This may reflect the fact that digital reforms can provide an effective means for cities to promote the optimization and transformation of their economic structure in an environment where market mechanisms are not

sufficiently developed, thus reducing dependence on traditional resources.

However, the relationship between digital reforms and resource dependence is no longer significant in more market-oriented cities. This implies that in highly marketized economies, the effects of digital reforms may be influenced by other market factors that make their impact on resource dependence weaker. These market factors may include higher levels of competition, more flexible resource allocation, and more mature industrial chains. In such environments, the marginal effects of digital reforms may be diluted by other

market dynamics.

Overall, these results underscore the central role of the degree of marketization in determining how digital reforms affect resource dependence. This provides valuable insights for governments and policymakers on the need to fully

consider the market environment in their cities when considering advancing digitization reforms to ensure that the reforms are effective in contributing to sustainable economic development.

Table 7. Results of the test for heterogeneity in the degree of marketisation

VARIABLES	(1)	(2)
	marketability Low RSD	High RSD
GDD	-0.0313*** (-3.5531)	-0.0030 (-0.5748)
Controls	Y	Y
Year	Y	Y
City	Y	Y
Constant	1.2171 (0.6637)	3.4386** (2.2932)
Observations	952	454
R-squared	0.9443	0.9651

5. MECHANISM ANALYSIS

Table 8 presents the regression results of the mediating effects. In column (1), GDD (GDD) is negatively correlated with LRM (LRM) at the 5% significant level, implying that digital reforms can reduce the degree of land resource misallocation. This may be due to the fact that the digital reform improves the transparency of land use, strengthens the regulation of land use, and thus promotes the efficient allocation of land resources. Further, in Column (2), LRM is positively correlated with RSD (RSD) at the 1% significant level, implying that a high degree of mismatch in land resources exacerbates dependence on natural resources. Combining these two findings, we can infer that GDD indirectly reduces natural resource dependence by reducing the mismatch of land resources.

GDD is positively correlated with DE (DE) in column (3) at the 10% level of significance, reflecting the significant boost of digital reforms to DE. This positive relationship may stem from the fact that digital reforms have increased the adoption of information technology, innovation, and access to digital services. However, when we consider the effect of DE on RSD, in Column (4), DE is negatively associated with RSD at the 1% significant level. This implies that the development of DE may lead to a structural transformation of

the economy from resource-intensive industries to technology- and service-oriented industries, thus reducing the dependence on natural resources. Therefore, GDD, by facilitating the rise of DE, in turn, reduces the dependence on natural resources.

In column (5), GDD is positively correlated with EC (EC) at 1% significant level, which may be attributed to the fact that digital reforms have enhanced the efficiency of information dissemination, making it easier for the public to access and share information on environmental issues. While in column (6), EC is negatively correlated with RSD (RSD) at the 5% level of significance, which suggests that public concern about environmental issues drives more sustainable and environmentally friendly policy choices, which in turn reduces dependence on natural resources.

Taken together, these mediating effects reveal that the impact of GDD on RSD is multifaceted and complex. GDD not only directly reduces resource dependence by optimizing land use, but also further reinforces this impact by promoting DE transformation and raising public environmental awareness. This provides the government with new perspectives and strategies to achieve sustainable resource use.

Table 8. Mediation effect test results

VARIABLES	(1) LRM	(2) RSD	(3) DE	(4) RSD	(5) EC	(6) RSD
GDD	-0.0123** (-1.9797)		0.0001* (1.8385)		0.0133*** (2.7456)	
LRM		0.0855*** (3.0454)				
DE				-11.9255*** (-3.5256)		
EC						-0.0706** (-2.2942)
Controls	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Year	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
City	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Constant	1.5203** (2.2865)	1.6978* (1.8307)	0.0038 (0.7360)	1.8734** (2.0163)	-0.2604 (-0.4607)	1.8104* (1.9526)
Observations	1,466	1,466	1,466	1,466	1,466	1,466
R-squared	0.4581	0.9378	0.8856	0.9379	0.5284	0.9376

6. CONCLUSIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND SHORTCOMINGS

6.1 Conclusions of the study

This paper provides a fresh perspective for exploring the resource curse problem, namely how GDD can provide a possible solution to alleviate this long-standing dilemma. Through a detailed analysis of Chinese prefecture-level city data from 2011-2020, we draw several revealing conclusions.

First, this study reveals that GDD, as a new type of governance tool, has a significant effect in mitigating the city's overdependence on natural resources. This not only implies that through the introduction and enhancement of digital tools, governments can manage resources more efficiently, but also implies that such reforms play a key role in promoting sustainable resource use.

Second, our findings show that the effects of GDD are not uniform across all regions. Specifically, the western region benefits the most, followed by the central region, while the eastern region benefits relatively little. This may be related to the resource endowment, economic structure and development stage of each region. More interestingly, in terms of city size, third- and fourth-tier cities benefit particularly significantly, which may be related to the specific challenges these cities face in resource allocation and digitization processes. In addition, this dampening effect is more pronounced in regions where digital finance and marketization are less developed.

Further, GDD is also closely linked to other important economic and social variables. For example, we find that GDD can promote DE, which not only opens up new avenues of growth for cities and reduces dependence on traditional resources, but also improves overall economic efficiency. In addition, as GDD advances, public attention to environmental issues increases, which implies higher demands for environmental protection and a stronger pursuit of sustainable development. Finally, GDD can also significantly improve LRM, which in turn reduces urban RSD.

6.2 Policy recommendations

From a governmental perspective, the government occupies a central position in promoting digitization reforms. Taking into account the findings of this study, it is recommended that the government further strengthen its investment in digitization projects, especially in the western and central regions, which are rich in resources but relatively lagging behind in economic development. The government should promote the application of digital technology in resource management, environmental protection and sustainable development strategies to ensure effective, fair and efficient utilization of resources. In addition, in order to make digital reform more effective, the Government should strengthen cooperation with local governments, enterprises and the public to ensure that policies are put into practice and implemented.

From the social point of view, with increasing public concern about environmental issues, all sectors of society should recognize the important role of digital reform in promoting sustainable development. The media, NGOs and educational institutions should increase the publicity of GDD results to enhance public awareness and participation. At the same time, society should encourage the public to actively participate in all aspects of digital reform, such as data collection, analysis and application, so as to ensure that the effects of the reform are maximized.

From an enterprise perspective, digitization was not only a technological advancement but also a shift in business models. Enterprises should seize the opportunities brought about by digitization, especially in resource management and environmental protection. By adopting digital technologies, enterprises could manage and use resources more efficiently, reduce costs and improve competitiveness. In addition, enterprises should build partnerships with government, society and other enterprises to promote digital reform and achieve common sustainable development goals.

6.3. Insufficient research

First, the simplification of the theoretical framework. In order to facilitate the analysis, this paper may oversimplify the relationship between GDD and RSD. In fact, this relationship may be affected by many other factors, such as government policies, technological progress, and international economic environment. Second, the lack of dynamic analysis. The theoretical analysis in this paper is mainly based on a static perspective and fails to fully consider the dynamic interaction between GDD and RSD. For example, the process and effects of GDD may change over time, and such changes may further affect its impact on RSD. Third, the lack of interdisciplinary integration. Although this paper provides insights from an economics perspective, it fails to fully integrate knowledge from other disciplines, such as sociology, psychology, and environmental science, which may provide more comprehensive and in-depth insights. In conclusion, although this paper provides an important theoretical framework and insights into the relationship between GDD and RSD, it still suffers from the research deficiencies mentioned above. Future research should consider these shortcomings and further deepen and extend the theoretical analysis in this paper.

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